

USERS' PERCEPTION OF LIGHTING IN HOSTELS ALONG KANU NWANKWO

ROAD, OWERRI NORTH, IMO STATE

BY

OMEIKE SOCHUKWU GERTRUDE

AND

ONYEKWERE PATRICK EKENE

DEPARTMENT OF ARCHITECTURE

FACULTY OF ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

IMO STATE UNIVERSITY, OWERRI

DECEMBER 2022

ABSTRACT

The role that lighting plays in buildings cannot be underestimated. Light is integrated into buildings because of its potential economic benefit and the effect on the occupants' psychological and physiological wellbeing. This study concentrates on hostels along Kanu Nwankwo road, in Owerri north, Imo state, where poor architectural designs could affect the performance of students. Therefore, the primary aim of this study is to highlight the importance of light in all dimensions and comfort level of both daylight and artificial light, in satisfaction to the perception of the user's and how to integrate proper lighting conditions in the hostels. Questionnaires and interviews, as well as empirical measuring of daylight levels in the spaces of selected hostels were used. Analysed data revealed that the level of illuminance in the hostels is considerably poor and this resulted in students using artificial lighting throughout the day. Nevertheless, the negative effect of this situation can be prevented from occurring in further developments in Owerri north by educating the public on the benefits of using natural lighting in buildings and by enforcing laws that will ensure that buildings have maximum openings that allow enough daylight into the interior spaces. These measures will help reduce utility costs, improve the well-being of building occupants and increase the performance of students.

CHAPTER 1; INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

The role of light inside a built space has seen a sea change starting with sunlight as the only source of light and slowly moving towards greater dependence on artificial sources of light. The last century has seen a tremendous shift with the advent of electrical lighting and its easy availability. The increasing need for control in the illumination levels inside a space has been emphasized through the use of static artificial lighting. The variation in the character and ambience of a space, with the movement of the sun across the sky and the changing seasons, has been sacrificed in the process. This shift while increasing the energy dependence has also made the interior devoid of a strong relation with the exterior. Primitive accounts on the use of natural light can be traced back to the strong rays of sun penetrating through the extreme darkness of a cave. All through this time, natural light has been a primary source for illumination used, with varying degrees of control, in different kinds of shelters built by human beings in pursuit for survival and comfort. The intuitive and artistic sense with which light openings have been carved of different surfaces has brought in a sense of place that is unique in so many different ways. Daylight has been associated with strong symbolic meanings in the way it was made to enter a space and cast shadows on different surfaces. This part of the literature review will focus on the use of natural light in its different manifestations inside the built environment in the context of their historical period. It will deal with the symbolic meanings of natural light as well as the manner in which it was controlled to create different effects inside a built environment.

Li, Cheung, Cheung, and Lam (2010) also identified natural lighting reflected from its nearby and ground buildings play certain roles in natural lighting design. The natural lighting that is available in the interior building depends on the amount of natural light enter the window area.

The daylight used in the buildings is very important for the physical comfort especially on visual and also human health-efficiency. Human spend most of their time inside of the building (Choi, 2012).

Phillips (2004) lays an emphasis on the history of windows and of daylighting, which he says is synonymous with the history of architecture. The nature of windows relates to the appearance of buildings. In mediaeval period, the shape and location of windows was related to the function and role they would perform in the overall daylighting of the interior spaces. This changed in the

Renaissance period as windows became formal objects seen as part of the elevation thus losing the connection with the interior spaces.

Natural lighting systems have been developed for improving natural lighting efficiency. The concept of natural lighting is to bring daylight into the buildings area. The benefit of using natural lighting is to reduce the use of artificial lighting. and directly using solar energy (Yeh, 2014).

The comfort level of inside buildings is quite highly related to daylight accessibility, which is depends on solar entree into the opening, irradiation on windows and doors, as well as solar lights (Ramírez, Pujols, Casares, Ramírez-Faz, & López-Luque, 2013)

1.2 Statement of problem

Kay (2009) found that the lighting needs intelligence and control. Nowadays most of a building's light that used natural lighting is wasted on fixtures that are too bright, uncontrollable, competing with sunlight, or illuminating empty spaces.

Most of students' hostel lack the important resources especially natural lighting. Openings of students' hostel are poorly designed or positioned. It has become a conventional practice that lighting in student hostel is achieved only through artificial lighting system. Poor opening design could be the fact which is giving a negative impact on the performance of students living in hostels. Lighting has both psychological and physiological impact on the life of an individual student life. During cloudy day or under poor lighting conditions, the inability to perceive the colors from light can affect our mood and energy level. This invariably, increases accidents, reduces mental performance and as a result, could decrease students' academic performance.

1.3 Aim

The aim of this paper is to highlight the importance of light in all dimensions and comfort level of both daylight and artificial light, in satisfaction to the perception of the user's and how to integrate proper lighting conditions in the hostels along Kaun Nwankwo road Owerri.

1.4 Objective

2. To identify the design features and problems which influence the natural lighting in hostel.
3. To measure the illuminance of natural lighting in the hostel.

4. To know student satisfaction on the concept of lighting that have been implemented in the building.

1.5 Research Questions

1. What are the design features and problems which influence the lighting in hostels?
2. How to measure the illuminance of natural lighting in the hostel?
3. What is the student satisfaction on the concept of lighting that have been implemented in the building?

1.6 Justification of study

In this study, two ways sources that use which is the primary and secondary sources. For the primary sources, data will be collected using certain test which is lux meter to get lux reading in the building. Besides that, questionnaire will be used to gain data which is will be distributed to students that occupy the building. For the secondary sources, data will be collected using previous studies such as from books, article, web page and other relevant reference

1.7 The study area

This study was carried out in Imo state in Owerri north local government area. The hostel to be study are Imo state university female hostel, merit hostel, and Steve James hostel located along Kanu Nwankwo road in Owerri, Imo state.

1.8 Scope of the study

The scope of study only covers on lighting that enter the room, student satisfaction on the concept of lighting that have been implemented in the building whether it comply with the regulation related to lighting

1.9 Significance of the study

Since there has not been much research regarding the quality of natural light by analyzing the space for different effects, this study provides an opportunity to address different issues related to light and expression of a space in a collective manner. The outcomes from this study could help designers in the use of light to design and articulate spaces. The methodology developed and tested in this study could form a basis for analyzing other architects use of natural light in public

spaces. A similar approach could be used for instructing design students in the configuration and articulation of spaces using natural light and artificial light.

1.10 Limitation of study

The limitation of study is only concentrated on the hostel along Kaun Nwankwo road Owerri in Imo state. The observation and measure of natural lighting will be done during day time because during night artificial light will be used in the building. To determine the effectiveness of natural lighting, a specific test will be carried out in this study using lux meter.

CHAPTER 2; LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Preamble

The perception of space is directly connected to the way light integrates with it. What we see, what we experience and how we interpret the elements is affected by how light interacts with us and with the environment. Regarding architecture, in whatever dimension it can be analyzed, either as space, as material or as color, it is essentially dependent on the lighting situation that involves both the object and the observer.

2.2 Conceptual framework

Before the 1940s, daylight was the primary light source in buildings; artificial lights supplemented the natural light. In the short span of 20 years, electric lighting had transformed the workplace by meeting most or all of the occupants' lighting requirements. Recently, energy and environmental concerns have made daylighting a rediscovered aspect of building lighting design. The physics of daylighting has not changed since its original use, but the building design to use it has. Daylighting is often integrated into a building as an architectural statement and for energy savings. However, benefits from daylighting extend beyond architecture and energy. The psychological and physiological aspects of natural light should also be considered. The comforting space and connection to the environment provided to building occupants provide benefits as significant as the energy savings to building owners and managers.

The perception of space is directly connected to the way light integrates with it. What we see, what we experience and how we interpret the elements is affected by how light interacts with us and with the environment. Regarding architecture, in whatever dimension it can be analyzed, either as space, as material or as color, it is essentially dependent on the lighting situation that involves both the object and the observer.

The dynamic daylight and the controlled artificial lighting are able to affect not only distinct physical measurable conditions in a space, but also to instigate and provoke different visual experiences and moods. Due to the light, it is possible to perceive different atmospheres in the same physical environment. Light constitutes an element of fundamental relevance for the design of spaces and therefore, it plays a significant role in the discussion of quality in architecture.

2.2.1 Planning and Process

The basis for every lighting concept is an analysis of the project the tasks the lighting is expected to fulfill, the conditions and special feature of a space or work surface. When it comes to qualitative planning, it is necessary to gain as much information as possible about the environment to be illuminated, how it is used, who will use it and the style of the architecture. A quantitative design concept can to a large extent follow the standards laid down for a specific task. Standards will dictate how much light is needed,

1. the degree of glare limitation,
2. the source color and color rendering.

Preliminary lighting concepts list the properties that lighting should possess: They may give no exact information about the choice of lamps or fixtures or their arrangement. Further analysis provides illumination guidelines giving information about the individual forms of lighting i.e. high light levels will need high performance fixtures and lamps, etc. The challenge of a qualitative lighting design is to develop a design concept that combines the technical and aesthetic requirements of complex guidelines. A concept that delivers the required performance with a equal level of technical expertise and the highest level of artistic clarity will produce the most convincing solution.

2.2.2 Planning and Process: Design Development

As the design phase progresses, decisions are made regarding the lamps and fixtures to be used the arrangement and installation of the fixtures any required electrical and control devices. The decision regarding lamp type can be made at the beginning of a project or left until an advanced planning stage. Lighting layouts (the plan) can be determined by the choice of a light fixture or could be the criteria for fixture selection. Lighting design process should be seen as a “back and forth” check in which developed solutions are repeatedly compared to the predetermined goals and requirements.

2.2.3 Vision

The fact that a medium grey area will appear light grey if it is bordered in black, or dark grey if it is bordered in white. This can be explained by the fact that the stimuli perceived are processed directly - brightness is perceived as a result of the lightness contrast between the grey area and the immediate surroundings. What we are considering here is a visual impression that is

based exclusively on sensory input which is not influenced by any criteria of order linked with our intellectual processing of this information.

Plate ;2.2.3 The perception of brightness of the grey field depends on the environment - in bright surroundings, an identical grey appears darker than in dark surroundings

2.2.4 Lighting Effects: Shadows and Gradient

The continuous luminance gradient across the surface of the wall is interpreted as a property of the lighting. The wall reflectance factor is assumed to be constant. The grey of the sharply framed picture is interpreted as a material property, although the luminance is identical to the luminance in the corner of the room.

Plate ; 2.2.4 A non-continuous luminance gradient across a surface may create confusion, misinformation, or the perception of darkness / gloom

2.2.5 Light and Perception

Fixed objects produce retinal images of varying shapes, sizes and brightness. Due to changes in lighting, distance or perspective, this indicates that mechanisms must exist to identify these objects and their properties and to perceive them as being constant. However, the quality of the light significantly depends on several aspects of the lighting system as luminance, illuminance

(intensity of light that impinges upon a surface), avoiding the glare, uniformity, distribution, and color contrast. Regarding illuminance there recommended range significantly depends on the need for visual activity and the age of the user, whereas for the maximum luminance ratio guidelines come with some recommendation., the range of luminance in the visual field.

2.2.6 Light in Architecture and Psychology of Light

I. The Three Elements of Light

- a) General or Ambient lighting provides an area with overall illumination. Also known as ambient lighting, general lighting radiates a comfortable level of brightness, enabling one to see and walk about safely.

Plate 2.2.6(a) showing general lighting in a work space

General or Ambient Lighting: General lighting provides uniform illumination over the entire area of a room, allowing flexibility in the placement of workstations. Localized general lighting also provides approximately uniform illumination, but luminaries are located in a pattern that responds to the specific arrangement of workstations.

- b) **Task Lighting or Lighting at the Work plane** helps you perform specific tasks such as reading, sewing, cooking, homework, hobbies, games, or balancing your checkbook.

Local or Task Lighting; Local Lighting provides high illumination on relatively small areas. It can be too bright and uncomfortable unless surrounding surfaces are also illuminated, as shown. Local lighting used with general lighting is called supplementary lighting

Plate 2.2.6(b); showing task lighting in a work space.

- c) Light or Highlighting adds drama to a room by creating visual interest. As part of a decorating scheme, it is used to spotlight paintings, houseplants, sculpture, and other prized possessions, or to highlight the texture of a wall, drapery or outdoor landscaping.

2.2.7 Light- physical and visual

Humans are affected both psychologically and physiologically by the different spectrums provided by the various types of light. These effects are the less quantifiable and easily overlooked benefits of daylighting. Daylighting has been associated with improved mood, enhanced morale, lower fatigue, and reduced eyestrain. One of the important psychological aspects from daylighting is meeting a need for contact with the outside living environment (Robbins 1986).

According to Dr. Ott (Ott Bio light Systems, Inc. 1997a), the body uses light as a nutrient for metabolic processes similar to water or food. Natural light stimulates essential biological functions in the brain and is divided into colors that are vital to our health. On a cloudy day or under poor lighting conditions, the inability to perceive the colors from light can affect our mood and energy level. Dr. Liberman (1994) also mentioned that light plays a role in maintaining health:

When we speak about health, balance, and physiological regulation, we are referring to the function of the body's major health keepers; the nervous system and the endocrine system. These major control centers of the body are directly stimulated and regulated by light, to an extent far beyond what modern science...has been willing to accept.

2.3 Theoretical framework

Light is a form of energy. It satisfies law of conservation of energy. According to this law, energy is neither created nor destroyed. It just converts from one format to another format. Hence another format of energy can be converted into light and the light also can be converted into other formats of energies. Light exhibits a wide variety of properties. They are reflection, refraction,

dispersion, interference, diffraction, polarization, photo electric effect, Compton Effect, Stark effect and Zeeman Effect. To explain all these properties of light, we have different theories of light. If the size of the object interacting with the light is much larger than the wavelength of the light with respect to the object, light appears like a straight line and all the corresponding concepts were studied under the topic called Ray optics. If the size of the object is comparable to the wavelength of the light, light appears like a wave and all the relevant topics are studied under the name wave optics or physical optics. The properties of light like interference, diffraction and polarization can be explained only by assuming that light is travelling like a wave. Right from the beginning of the human evolution, human beings are very much interested in understanding the properties of light. In this process different theories are proposed. Each theory is having its own advantages and failures and here we are going to have brief discussion of the concepts.

1. Newton's corpuscular theory

Among different theories, Newton's corpuscular theory is first one. According to this theory light is a stream of tiny particles called corpuscles. This tiny particle carries energy by moving along straight lines. There are different colours of the light. According to this theory, it is due to different sizes of corpuscles. It is assumed that this tiny particles travels with enormous velocity. This theory is successful in explaining the concepts of reflection and refraction. Anyway, this theory is having some issues. According to this theory, velocity of the light is more in denser medium than the rarer medium. But practically it is proved that velocity of the light is actually more in the rarer medium and this theory failed to explain why. As the light is leaving the source like particles, mass of the source shall decrease but that is not happening. This theory failed to explain how reflection and refraction can happen simultaneously. To address all these issues a new theory called Huygens wave theory is proposed.

2. Huygens wave theory

According to this theory light is not traveling like a straight line but it travels like a wave. He assumed that light wave is mechanical in nature which demands a medium for propagation. Hence a invisible, highly elastic low-density medium is imagined all-around and it is called ether medium. He also proposed a principle called Huygens principle to explain the wave propagation. This theory is successful in explaining that velocity of the light is more in the rarer medium than the denser medium and hence the problem is solved. This theory is also successful in explaining the phenomena like interference and diffraction. But this theory is also having some problems. It fails to explain the concept of polarization. It also failed to explain photo electric effect and all other modern-day effects

of light. Experimentally it is proved that there is no imagined medium that is filled over the entire space and hence there is no exact way to explain how the wave is propagating from one place to another place. To solve all these problems electromagnetic wave theory is proposed was proposed by Maxwell.

3. Electromagnetic wave theory

According to this theory light propagates like an electromagnetic wave and it doesn't need any medium for propagation. A variable electric field generates a variable magnetic field around it and the propagation of the wave is perpendicular to both of them. Because it is a non-mechanical wave, we don't need any medium for propagation itself. The wave equations that we have written in waves and oscillations are valid in explaining the propagation of electric and magnetic fields. Basing on the permittivity and the permeability of the vacuum we can define the velocity of the light. It is proved that velocity of light is constant and is maximum in the vacuum. According to this theory, velocity of light in any other is less than the velocity of the light in vacuum. This theory is successful in explaining the concepts like interference, diffraction and polarization. At the same time this theory is unable to explain how the photoelectric effect and Compton Effect are happening. To address this problem Plank's quantum theory is proposed.

4. Plank's quantum theory

According to Plank's quantum theory, light is not travelling like a wave rather it is travelling like a small packet of energy called quanta. Energy is not emitted by the source continuously but discretely in the form of wave packets. This theory is successful in explaining the modern-day properties of the light like photoelectric effect and Compton Effect. But simultaneously it is unable to explain the concepts like interference, diffraction and polarization. Hence, we do not have a unified theory which can explain all the properties of light. So it is assumed that light travels like a wave and exhibits certain set of properties and when it interacts with someone, it interacts like a particle and exhibits the modern-day properties. This concept is called dual nature of the light.

5. Huygens principle

According to this principle, every point the primary wave front behaves like a secondary source and propagates the light in the forward direction. Wave front is the locus of all the points that are in the same phase. The wave front from a point source is spherical in nature whereas the wave front from the cylindrical source is cylindrical in nature. As we move far away from the point source, the radius of the spherical wave front increases to a larger value so that it appears like a plane wave front.

2.3.1 Principle of natural lighting

Natural lighting is the best approach when natural lighting is used to substitute artificial lighting. Natural lighting can improve the quality of lighting in buildings and can reduce heat, saving on energy cost (Dr Peter Lyons, n.d.).

The geometry of the space, the location and orientation of window and other opening and the characteristics of the internal surface is the factors that determine the level and distribution of natural lighting at the building. Daylight design prepared enough light suits with activities carried out in the building following the requirement for room space, design and aesthetic of the buildings

Lighting design is an important issue for sustainable buildings which includes both setting natural and artificial lights as well as meeting energy distribution goals (Ferna, 2012).

Daylight is an interesting light source, but it should be controlled (through solar shading, dosing and/or redirecting of the natural light) in order to make it useful for lighting the working environment. Even in the best daylight buildings, a need remains for complementary or substituting artificial lighting. With daylight responsive control system daylight can be used to decrease the energy consumption for electric lighting (International Energy Agency, 2001).

The level and distribution of natural light within a space depends primarily upon the following three factors: The geometry of the space, the location and orientation of windows and other openings, and the characteristics of the internal surfaces. Daylighting design shapes these factors to accommodate the lighting requirements of activities within the space and the esthetic intent of the design. Certain usage patterns require particular light levels and overall distribution patterns.

2.3.2 Strategies of natural lighting

Based on (Green Building Tech HK, 2007), there are two types of daylight strategies which is lighting from side and lighting from the top. Lighting from the side and from the top are the main categories of the strategies. The system of day lighting will depend on the orientation and the layout and the building surroundings. Lighting from side is a technique that let the sunlight penetrates into a room opening located at the wall perimeter. Lighting from top is a technique that provides daylight from the upper part of the building. It gives out an evenly illuminance to the

entire top floor area of a building. Top lighting comprises of roof monitors, saw tooth roofs and skylights.

Plate 2.3.2(a) Standard Side Lighting Concept Source: (Green Building Tech HK, 2007)

Figure 2.3.2 shows the Standard of side lighting concept. Side lighting is a method that carries sunlight over openings positioned in the perimeter walls of a building. Those openings include curtain wall or further continuous fenestration arrangements. To make the most of the sunlight diffusion and decrease opening glare and brightness, it is a worthy practice to detach the view opening from the sunlight opening. The sunlight glazing is placed as near to the ceiling as possible for bouncing sunlight deep into the room by the ceiling. In this way, higher visible transmission glazing can be used in the sunlight opening.

According to (International Energy Agency, 2001), first thing to control the amount and distribution of daylight entering a space, the window size and position in the façade determine mostly the utilization of daylight. Secondly, the transmission characterization of the glazing determines the transmittance a day lighting system based on window size. It is then being dimensioned. A day lighting system is an adaptation of the window aimed at improving the amount and distribution of daylight in the space

Plate 2.3.2(b) windows category source: (David Leo, 1999)

According to Loe (1999), side windows have the benefit that they allow sight of the outside, at the right level and there are no disturbing windowpanes to block this view at sitting and standing eye level spots for children and adults. It is commonly for trees, other buildings and rising ground to cause an obstacle in the case of side windows, though there is an externally reflected piece of light from these obstacles.

Windows category	Diagram	Features
Side Windows		Usually located at the wall of the building
Clerestory windows		Arrow shows the location of clerestory window. Location usually at upper part of a building, near to roof
Roof lights		Clear materials are usually used for roofing (e.g sunlight roof) to allow natural lights entering the building.
Borrowed lights		Borrowed lights are lighting from adjacent room that receive source of lighting

Table 2.3.2(a) summary of window categories

Clerestory windows permits lights from the sunnier part of the sky and this is not likely to be obstructed. A vital characteristic of clerestory windows (high level window) is that it can deliver daylight deep into a space. Clerestory windows are commonly found in single storey. Roof lights also permit light from the highest and brightest part of the sky, and normally will not being disturbed by external obstacle. They have the probability to deliver smoother pattern of light. It goes without saying that simple roof lights can only be employed in single storey buildings or on the top floor of multi-storey buildings. In certain cases, borrowed light can make an input to the light levels in areas remote from window walls.

Plate 2.3.2(b) and location of windows affects the way in which daylight is dispersed, widespread narrow windows giving a broad dispersal and tall narrow windows gives a deep but narrow.

Discomfort can be experienced when some parts of an interior space have higher luminance than its environments. Discomfort glare from daylight can be a more common occurrence than disability glare, and under most conditions its degree will be influenced by not the window size or shape, but on the luminance of the sky seen in the universal direction of view.

Some lessening in the sky glare can be achieved by decreasing the contrast between the window and its environments, for example, by the use of spread light-colored exposes or increasing the illumination of the window wall by growing its reflectance. Window frames should be as lights color as possible, whether stained or painted timber, or painted or integrally colored metal or plastic. The reduction of the sky luminance is the major consideration, and where this is likely to be a problem provision should be made for blinds (vertical louvre blinds) or curtains.

I. Importance of Daylight

“Working long-term in electric lighting is believed to be deleterious to health; working by daylight is believed to result in less stress and discomfort. Daylight provides high illuminance and permits excellent color discrimination and color rendering. These two properties mean that daylight provides the condition for good vision. However, daylight can also produce uncomfortable solar glare and very high luminance reflections on display screens, both of which interfere with good vision. Thus, the effect of daylight on the performance of tasks depends on how the daylight is delivered. All of these factors need to be considered in daylighting design for buildings.”(Nancy Ruck, 2000)

Based on (the greenage, n.d.), the natural lighting from daylight is so beneficial in two ways;

- 1) Daylight is free
- 2) Major health benefits for building occupant

Using daylight to light the space that use less artificial light is needed to illuminate the space, especially in business. The major advantages of daylight is for the building occupant, and its ability to better regulate the circadian cycle. Our internal circadian clocks regulate the timing of sleepiness and wakefulness throughout the day over each 24 hours period. Exposure of daylighting especially in the morning helps stimulate the wakefulness by throwing out the natural hormone that is called cortisol that helps to maximize memory functions as well as making us more alert. The exposure of daylight in morning also triggers the production of melatonin which is associated with sleep onset and normally gets produced when it goes dark. Another daylighting

benefit is improving the mood of building occupant who have access to more interesting external visual stimuli.

Nigerian Standard (NS) : 2017 “national building energy efficiency code ” has stated that requirement for indoor light depends on the task to be carried out for work environments. Typical lighting requirements for a variety of tasks are given below Table 2.3.2 Based on Table 2.3.2 the lighting standard that being used was the “Lighting for working interiors, for reading and writing” since students do their reading and writing mostly at their room. The required illuminance (lux) was between range 300-400.

Task and example of application	Illuminance (Lux)
Lighting to frequently used areas	
Minimum service illuminance	20
Interior walkway and car- park	50
Corridor, passageways, stairs	100
Entrance and Exit	100
Entrance hall, lobbies, waiting room	100
Gate house	200
frequent reading and writing	200

Table 2.3.2(b) : Typical lighting requirements in Nigerian Standard (NS): 2017 “national building energy efficiency code”

2.4 Historical framework

The role of natural light inside a built space has seen a sea change starting with sunlight as the only source of light and slowly moving towards greater dependence on artificial sources of light. The last century has seen a tremendous shift with the advent of electrical lighting and its easy availability. The increasing need for control in the illumination levels inside a space has been emphasized through the use of static artificial lighting. The variation in the character and ambience of a space, with the movement of the sun across the sky and the changing seasons, has been sacrificed in the process. This shift while increasing the energy dependence has also made the

interior devoid of a strong relation with the exterior. Primitive accounts on the use of natural light can be traced back to the strong rays of sun penetrating through the extreme darkness of a cave. All through this time, natural light has been a primary source for illumination used, with varying degrees of control, in different kinds of shelters built by human beings in pursuit for survival and comfort. The intuitive and artistic sense with which light openings have been carved of different surfaces has brought in a sense of place that is unique in so many different ways. Daylight has been associated with strong symbolic meanings in the way it was made to enter a space and cast shadows on different surfaces.

Phillips (2004) lays an emphasis on the history of windows and of daylighting, which he says is synonymous with the history of architecture. The nature of windows relates to the appearance of buildings. In mediaeval period, the shape and location of windows was related to the function and role they would perform in the overall daylighting of the interior spaces. This changed in the Renaissance period as windows became formal objects seen as part of the elevation thus losing the connection with the interior spaces. For military needs, slit windows with splayed sides were used to reduce the overall contrast as the light would spread along the interior wall surface. Indirect lighting was used in the baroque churches of southern Germany from windows concealed of a direct view from the congregation. Vertical windows in the external façade had been used throughout, but it was the use of roof lights to allow daylight in the central part of the building that had an influence on the stately homes of the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. This gave the architect freedom in the layout of the central areas in the plan that could receive daylight from different kinds of openings on the roof

The modern movement in England in the 1930s saw the use of full walls of glass and wrap-around windows at corners. This was one of the earliest attempts aimed at expressing the freedom in the relation between the exterior and the interior. On the same note the growth of the workplace in the nineteenth century had seen a need for higher levels of illumination, thus forcing a greater dependence on a controlled environment where primary illumination was achieved through artificial lighting. The ever-increasing use of artificial lighting led to windowless built environments by the middle of the 1960s, thus raising questions regarding the association of the interior with the natural environment and its importance.

2.4 Empirical framework

Building types are not buildings. The conversion from a general building type to a particular building consents for a site-specific architectural quality and response. Building types can be adjusted to fit specific metropolitan backgrounds. A specific location arrangement may

accommodate a range of building types. A building can be a hybrid building type which is a mixture of more than one type and in greater developments, an addition of building types may be applicable. Multiple building types may apply to single site and deliver extra design choice.

Based on Study tech (2015) student accommodation can be categorized into two classes. Which are on-campus and off-campus place. Normally, the type of accommodation selected depends on a student's routine and budget. These are accommodations provided by the college or university. On-campus student accommodation can be in the form of halls of residence or university-owned apartments.

The present research is aimed at analyzing spaces where lighting issues are of utmost importance. In other words, these spaces could be categorized under 'subjective installations' that cannot be dealt with the conventional methods that are based on luminance values. These spaces have been designed to create a character by experimenting with different effects of natural light. To analyze the lighting design in these spaces, one needs to approach the subject based on the visual perception of the observer. The lighting design cannot be treated in isolation from the architecture of the space.

CHAPTER 3; RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Preamble

Research methodology can be used as a guideline and planning to do a research from the beginning of it until the end. This research is going to be conducted to identify the Satisfaction of Lighting at the hostel located along Kanu Nwankwo road Owerri.

3.2 Research design

- The first step in carrying out this research would be identifying the research problems, issues and scope of research. The selected study is selected after choosing three case study. The research of this study will then have established, the results out come with three strong objectives which is to measure the lighting that have been installed in the building ensuring that it comply with standard using certain test.
- The second objective is to identify the design of the lighting adapted in building.
- The last objective is to identify satisfaction of students towards lighting that is implied at their hostel.

3.3 Sampling

The case study of this research will be conducted at hostels along Kanu Nwankwo road will be selected for this research. The selected case study would be the imo state university female hostel, Merit hostel and Steve James hostel .The investigation of this research will depend on the students who lived in the hostel as the respondents and the basic questions will answer for their age, study program and number and floor room and also about their satisfaction on natural lighting at their room. A daily routines and satisfaction with day lighting conditions at their rooms, especially during either morning, midday afternoon and evening, how they grade their room regarding natural light and comfort for studying and etc. All of these questions will influence how the data that will be collected.

3.3.1 Population

The selections of the case studies are determined by the scope of area which is along Kanu Nwankwo road. The chosen locations were;

- Imo state university female hostel
- Merit hostel
- Steve James hostel

Hostels	Number of rooms	Number of students
Imo state university female hostel	96	130
Merit hostel	36	48
Steve James hostel	50	72

Table 3.3.1 showing the population of students in the hostels

3.3.2 Sampling frame

The range at which this study is carried out in the hostel which is along Kanu Nwankwo road Owerri. These hostels are; Imo state university Female hostel is a three storey building with each floor accommodating 16 rooms. Each room accommodates a minimum of 1 and a maximum of 3 inmates with individual reading space that comprises of a table and chair, it sums up to a total of 130 students. Merit hostel is a one storey building with each floor accommodating 18 rooms. It accommodates a total of 48 students. Steve James hostel is a two storey building with boys' quarters, having a sum total of 50 rooms, having 42 rooms in the building and 8 in the boys' quarters. The hostels are allocated to the students of Imo State University.

3.3.3 Sampling method

There are a lot of sampling methods which are grouped into two categories which are grouped into two categories as

- Probability sampling
- Non - probability sampling

The sampling method used is the probability sampling. This method uses randomization to make sure that every element of the population gets an equal chance to be part of the selected sample. Stratified sampling is a sub type of probability sampling, the method divides the elements of the population into small subgroups (strata) based on the similarity in such a way that the elements within the group are homogeneous and heterogeneous among the other subgroups formed. Therefore, since the building is divided in floors, the questionnaire will be handed out at a selection amount at each floor.

3.3.4 Sampling size

The measure of the number of individual samples used in the survey is 100. The number of questionnaires handed out was 100 but the total amount of respondents is 86.

3.4 Methods of data collection

The method that is used on this case study is a combination of qualitative and quantitative method. It is involved an observation, questionnaires and test. The data needed for this study will be obtained based on the question provided in the questionnaires and lux meter reading in (lx). The data mostly focus on the natural lighting satisfaction and level of comfort to the building occupant. The questionnaire consists of 2 sections which is section A and B and comprises of 6 questions. The rating of the question will be start with asking the respondent's name, age, and also study program. After collecting data, the data then will be analyzed and be presented in table, graph, pie, and chart for

3.4.1 Data types and sources

Data collection is the phase where both primary and secondary data will be used to gain an adequate data. The data need to be sufficient to provide enough evidence to help the researcher conducting his research. The primary data is the main approach to gain data on natural lighting. It consists of questionnaire and conducting lux meter test. The secondary data is included in the literature review which will be as a guideline to the researcher to finish his research.

1. Primary Data

- Lux Meter Test

In carrying out this research, lux meter test is used. A table is prepared by the researcher in a paper. Lux meter test requires the lux meter as equipment to measure the natural lighting that penetrates into the student's room. The data obtained will be tabulate on data analysis and graphed. The data gained will be compared to the standards of the natural lighting requirement. The test is carried out at selected student's room only at daytime. The periods of time are counted starting from morning, mid-day, afternoon, and evening. It is referring to the time of 8.00 AM to 6.00 PM. This test is for determining the illuminance reading of a room or a place. After the reading is gained, it needs to be records on a piece of paper, being tabled, and graphed. The reading then will be compared to the standard and any other regulations on natural lighting requirements on a building. In conducting this test, anything that will influence the reading needs to be taken care of. As this research is on the natural lighting focus only, any artificial lights need to be put off so that the reading of the test won't be affected.

2. Secondary Data

This method of finding data is the second approach to help the researcher support his data gain from the questionnaire and also the test. This method will use the collection through reading some

books, journals, web pages, articles and other references. The key words of LIGHTING on the searching will be used so that more data gained to use as the literature review . From literature review, it gives the researcher the idea of how to control the scope of the questionnaire that he will design.

3.4.2 Research instrument

Plate 3.4.2(a) Lux Meter

Lux meter is for measuring illuminance. It is very mobile equipment that is very easy to carry that have a light detection sensor. (I. d. H. Occupational safety and health branch, 2008). “Lux meters for measuring brightness in lux or cd/m^2 . Some lux meters are equipped with internal memory or a data logger to record the measurements.

Plate 3.4.2(b) lux meter diagram

- Firstly, the battery must be connected, and then the button “ON” is pressed.
- The range selection switch to desired range is pressed.
- The photo detector cap must be removed and faced to light source in a horizontal position.
- The test value from the LCD display can be read.
- Data-Hold mode: to select the Hold model, the HOLD key is pressed

- When the measurement is completed, the photo detector cap is replaced and the power selector is turned OFF.

3.5 Validation and reliability

To measure the adequacy of illuminance in a workplace, a test must be carried out. (I. d. H. Occupational safety and health branch, 2008)

- The first step in carrying out the test is, the work area must be cleared out and being divided into an equal small square area. As example, if the area of a workspace is less than fifty meter per square, and the lighting found was at the height of two point five metre, the area will be divided into small squares of sixteen. In universal, if the work area is large, more small squares are recommended. (I. d. H. Occupational safety and health branch, 2008)

Plate 3.5(a):work of are a source:(I. d H.) Occupational safety and health branch, 2008

Based on (I. d. H. Occupational safety and health branch, 2008), Illuminance measurement will be taken at the center of each square with lux meter. The results then will be informed and indicate whether the lighting is well-distributed. The average value of the measurement will determine on the average for the work area illuminance. To determine whether the reading obtain is appropriate, it is needed to be compared to the standard illuminance reading. To determine whether the reading of illuminance is sufficient, the illuminance average need to be compared to the recommended average illumination for the task. To measure illuminance at its task position, the illuminance measurement needs to be taken at the work plane height. If there is no specified plane for the task, it should be taken on around 0.8 meter horizontal plane, above the floor. The luxmeter light sensor is then being placed on the work plane horizontally

Plate 3.5(c):illuminance measurement at desk source:(l. d. H. Occupational safety and health branch,2008)

3.6 Data collection and processing

Questionnaire design for structured questionnaire was divided into two (2) sections. Every section has its different aim and goal that function in identifying the information on Satisfaction of Natural Lighting at the three case studies. The method of answering the questionnaires in section A and section B is in the form of ticking answer. After collection of data complete, it will be analyzed by the researcher, be presented in bar chart or table or pie chart.

3.7 Data Analysis

Data analysis is the phase where all the data gained being summarized, being tabled, and graphed out. The questionnaire will determine the comfort level of the building occupant towards the illuminance of the space and leads to the suggestion of preventing any discomfort factor of the lighting in the building. The data gain must achieve the requirement from the objectives. If the objectives are not achieved, there must be something wrong with the procedure of conducting this research. The data gain is the final results in formulating the conclusion of the research and also the recommendation of the research.

CHAPTER 4; DATA PRESENTATION ANALYSES AND FINDINGS

In this chapter, the data collected were referred to objectives which are to identify the design features and problems which influence the natural lighting in residential college, to measure the illuminance of natural lighting in residential college, and to recommend the best practice of building design features. The first data collection was on the lux metre test (in lux) result that were measured at certain point of the case study. (refer plan at appendices). The second data collection was the one from respondents answering questionnaire given to them regarding their thoughts on natural lighting application at their college and SPSS software used to acquire the statistic. The lux meter data also was analyzed using Microsoft Excel to transport graphs.

4.1 Sun Direction on Study Area

Plate 4.1 Sun direction

source; author (2022)

The figure above shows imsu back gate overall plan indicating the sunrise and sunset. The location of the case study is circled in red.

4.2 Data on the Imo state university girls' hostel

Plate 4.2 (a) showing Imo state university girls hostel, which is a three storey building.

Plate Fig 4.2.(b) showing the type of window used in the girl's hostel.

Plate Fig 4.2(c) showing the corridor of the girl's hostel

Plate 4.2(d) showing the floor plan of Imo state university girls hostel floor plan
source; author(2022)

Plate 4.2 (e) Schematic floor plan of the girl’s hostel, a room showing measurement locations
source: Author, (2022)

From figure above, P1 until P4 refers to the point taken by the researcher to measure lux reading using lux meter. At every point, there will be 3 reading and result the from 3 reading, it comes out one average reading. According to the schematic floor plan, there is 2 point by the window and 2 each point at the other corner of the room.

4.2.2 Interview survey data: Imo state university girls’ hostel

Places student chose to study				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Room	18	42.9	42.9	42.9
School	15	35.7	35.7	78.6
Others	9	21.4	21.4	100
Total	42	100	100	

Table 4.2.1 (a) Places students chooses to study

Fig 4.2.1(a) Places student chose to study

Respondents at Imo state university girls' hostel are 42 students. From the bar chart in figure 4.1.1 (a), most of the respondents choose their room to study. 42.9% of respondents choose to study at room, followed by school with 35.7% and lastly 21.4% at other places. Respondent number 1 at girl's hostel chooses to study at corridor, respondent number 6 chooses to study at the ETF building and respondent number 23 chooses to study at corridor. The other two was not mention by the respondents.

Period students chooses to study most in a typical study day				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
morning	15	35.7	35.7	35.7
Mid-day	4	9.5	9.5	45.2
Afternoon	3	7.1	7.1	52.3
Evening/night	20	47.6	47.6	100
total	42	100	100	

Table 4.2.1 (b) Period students chooses to study most in a typical study day.

Figure 4.2.1 (b) Period students chooses to study most in a typical study day

Since the respondents are all students, there are very few of respondents chooses to study in the morning, mid-day or afternoon. This is because students went to class during the day. So, most of

the respondents with 47.6% choose to study at evening/night. The least is only 7.1% people which are at afternoon. The cause might be bad lighting condition in the room.

Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours less than 9 am				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Excellent	3	7.1	7.1	7.1
Good	12	28.6	28.6	35.7
Fair	19	45.2	45.2	80.2
Poor	8	19.1	19.1	100
total	42	100	100	

Table 4.2.1 (c) Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours less than 9 am

Figure 4.2.1 (c) Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours less than 9 am

Only 45.2% of the respondents agreed that the day lighting conditions in their rooms less than 9 am is fair. While only 7.1% of the respondents said that it is very excellent, these respondents mostly live at the top floor and usually sunlight during sunrise is not really glary.

Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 9 am to 12 noon				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent

Excellent	10	23.8	23.8	23.8
Good	8	19.1	19.1	42.9
Fair	18	42.8	42.8	85.7
Poor	6	14.3	14.3	100
total	42	100	100	

Table 4.2.1 (d) Opinion on the day lighting conditions in room 9 am to 12 noon

Figure 4.2.1 (d) Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 9 am to 12 noon

From figure 4.2.2 (d), it shows that most of the respondents chooses “fair” as their opinion on the day lighting conditions in their room from 9 am to 12 noon. At this hour, the sun was at the peak.

Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 12 noon to 3 pm				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Excellent	9	21.4	35.7	35.7
Good	19	45.2	19.1	31
Fair	8	19.1	26.2	81
Poor	6	14.3	19.1	100
total	42	100	100	

Table 4.2.1 (e) Opinion on the day lighting conditions in room 12 noon to 3 pm

Figure 4.2.1 (e) Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 12 noon to 3pm

From figure 4.2.2 (e), “good” has almost the same percentage. 45% of respondents said it was “fair” and 21.4% of the respondent said that it was “excellent” on the opinion of the day lighting conditions in their room during 12 noon to 3 pm. This shows that the orientation of the building plays a main role influencing the day lighting entrance to the students ‘room.

	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Excellent	5	11.9	11.9	11.9
Good	13	31	31	42.9
Fair	14	33.3	33.3	76.2
Poor	10	23.8	23.8	100
total	42	100	100	

Table 4.2.1 (f) Opinion on the day lighting conditions in room 3 pm to 6 pm

Figure 4.2.1 (f) Opinion on the day lighting conditions in room 3 pm to 6 pm

Figure 4.2.2 (f) shows that most of the respondents with 33.3% choose “fair” as their opinion on day lighting conditions in their room from 3 pm to 6 pm. The lowest said that it is “excellent” are rooms located at the ground floor of the building

Frequent activity in room				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Reading	18	42.9	42.9	42.9
Writing by hand	10	23.8	23.8	66.7
Working with laptop	4	9.5	9.5	76.2
others	10	23.8	23.8	100
total	42	100	100	

Table 4.2.1 (g) Frequent activity in the room

Figure 4.2.1 (g) Frequent activity in the room.

From figure 4.2.2 (g), most of the students choose to read in their individual room more than other activity with 42.9%, followed by 23.8% writing by hand and others (relaxing, sleeping

Frequently turn on the lamp (artificial lighting)				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Throughout the day	16	38.1	38.1	38.1
In the morning	12	28.6	28.6	66.7

In the evening	14	33.3	33.3	100
total	42	100	100	

Table 4.2.1 (i) use of the lamp (artificial lighting)

Fig 4.2.1 (i) use of the lamp (artificial lighting)

From figure above, the respondents mostly use the lamp throughout the day. While 33.3% turn on the lamp in the evening. 28.6% of the respondents turn on the lamp in the morning. This might be contributing to electrical wastage. It also shows that the daylighting was not active in certain room that causes the respondents to turn on the lamp throughout the day.

Frequent opening of the window during the day while studying				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Yes	38	90.5	90.5	90.5
No	4	9.5	9.5	100
total	42	100	100	

Table 4.2.1 (j) Frequent opening of the window during the day while studying

Fig 4.2.1 (j) Frequent opening of the window during the day while studying

Figure 4.2.2 (j) shows the percentage of an ordinal scale question, how frequent the respondents open the window during the day while studying. Most of the respondents open the window during the day while studying, a percentage of 90.5% , equals to 38 persons out of 42.

4.3 Data collect from Merit Hostel

Plate 4.3(a) showing merit hostel located along kanu Nwankwo road

Plate 4.3.(b) showing merit hostel court yard

Plate 4.3(c) showing the type of window used in merit hostel

Plate 4.3(d) showing the floor plan of merit hostel

Source (2022)

Plate 4.3 (e) Schematic floor plan of the merit hostel, a room showing measurement locations

source: Author, (2022)

4.3.1 Interview survey data: merit hostel

Places student chose to study				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Room	8	61.5	61.5	61.5
School	2	15.4	15.4	76.9
Others	3	23.1	23.1	100
Total	13	100	100	

Table 4.3.1 (a) Places students chooses to study

Fig 4.3.1 (a) Places students chooses to study

Period students chooses to study most in a typical study day				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
morning	4	30.8	30.8	30.8
Mid-day	2	15.4	15.4	46.2
Afternoon	0	0	0	0
Evening/night	7	53.8	53.8	100
total	13	100	100	

Table 4.3.1 (b) Period students chooses to study most in a typical study day

Figure 4.3.1 (b) Period students chooses to study most in a typical study day

Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours less than 9 am				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Excellent	0	0	0	0
Good	0	0	0	0
Fair	5	38.5	38.5	38.5
Poor	8	61.5	61.5	100
total	13	100	100	

Table 4.3.1 (c) Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours less than 9 am

Figure 4.3.1(c) Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours less than 9 am

Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 9 am to 12 noon				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Excellent	5	38.5	38.5	38.5
Good	6	46.2	46.2	84.7
Fair	2	15.3	15.3	100
Poor	0	0	0	100
total	13	100	100	

Table 4.3.1 (d) Opinion on the day lighting conditions in room 9 am to 12 noon

Figure 4.3.1 (d) Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 9 am to 12 noon

Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 12 noon to 3 pm				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Excellent	8	61.5	61.5	61.5
Good	4	30.8	30.8	92.3
Fair	1	7.7	7.7	100
Poor	0	0	0	100
total	13	100	100	

Table 4.3.1 (e) Opinion on the day lighting conditions in room 12 noon to 3 pm

Figure 4.3.1 (e) Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 12 noon to 3pm

Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 3 pm to 6 pm				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Excellent	6	46.2	46.2	46.2
Good	3	23.1	23.1	69.3
Fair	3	23.1	23.1	92.4
Poor	1	7.6	7.6	100
total	13	100	100	

Table 4.2.1 (f) Opinion on the day lighting conditions in room 3 pm to 6 pm

Figure 4.3.1 (f) Opinion on the day lighting conditions in room 3 pm to 6 pm

Frequent activity in room				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Reading	6	46.2	46.2	46.2
Writing by hand	2	15.4	15.4	61.6
Working with laptop	1	7.7	7.7	69.3
others	4	30.7	30.7	100
total	13	100	100	

Table 4.2.1 (g) Frequent activity in room

Figure 4.3.1 (g) Frequent activity in the room

Frequently turn on the lamp (artificial lighting)				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Throughout the day	7	53.8	53.8	53.8
In the morning	4	30.7	30.7	84.5
In the evening	2	15.4	15.4	100
total	13	100	100	

Table 4.3.1 (i) use of the lamp (artificial lighting)

Fig 4.3.1 (i) use of the lamp (artificial lighting)

Frequent opening of the window during the day while studying				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent

Yes	10	76.9	76.9	76.9
No	3	23.1	23.1	100
total	13	100	100	

Table 4.3.1 (j) Frequent opening of the window during the day while studying

Fig 4.3.1 (j) Frequent opening of the window during the day while studying

4.4 DATA COLLECTED FROM STEVE JAMES

Plate 4.4(a) showing Steve James hostel

Plate Fig 4.4(b) showing the corridor leading to the rooms

Plate 4.4 (c) showing the type of window used in the hostel

Plate 4.4(d) showing the floor plan of merit hostel

Source (2022)

Plate 4.4(e) Schematic floor plan of the merit hostel, a room showing measurement locations

source: Author, (2022)

4.4.1 Interview survey data: Steve James hostel

Places student chose to study				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Room	17	54.8	54.8	54.8

School	6	74.2	74.2	74.2
Others	8	25.8	25.8	100
Total	31	100	100	

Table 4.4.2 (a) Places students chooses to study

Fig 4.4.2 (a) Places students chooses to study

Period students chooses to study most in a typical study day				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
morning	12	38.7	38.7	38.7
Mid-day	0	0	0	0
Afternoon	1	3.2	3.2	41.9
Evening/night	18	58.1	58.1	100
total	31	100	100	

Table 4.4.2 (b) Period students chooses to study most in a typical study day.

Figure 4.4.2 (b) Period students chooses to study most in a typical study day

Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours less than 9 am				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Excellent	2	6.5	6.5	6.5
Good	5	16.1	16.1	22.6
Fair	12	38.7	38.7	61.3
Poor	12	38.7	38.7	100
total	31	100	100	

Table 4.4.2 (c) Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours less than 9 am

Figure 4.4.2(c) Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours less than 9 am

Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 9 am to 12 noon				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Excellent	4	12.9	12.9	12.9
Good	9	29	29	41.9
Fair	12	38.7	38.7	80.6
Poor	6	19.4	19.4	100
total	31	100	100	

Table 4.4.2 (d) Opinion on the day lighting conditions in room 9 am to 12 noon

Figure 4.4.2 (d) Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 9 am to 12 noon

Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 12 noon to 3 pm				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Excellent	9	29	29	29
Good	12	38.7	38.7	67.7
Fair	5	16.1	16.1	83.8
Poor	5	16.1	16.1	100
total	31	100	100	

Table 4.4.2 (e) Opinion on the day lighting conditions in room 12 noon to 3 pm

Figure 4.4.2 (e) Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 12 noon to 3pm

Opinion on day lighting condition in the room in hours of 3 pm to 6 pm				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Excellent	6	19.4	19.4	19.4
Good	10	32.3	32.3	51.7
Fair	7	22.6	22.6	74.3
Poor	8	25.8	25.8	100
total	31	100	100	

Table 4.4.2 (f) Opinion on the day lighting conditions in room 3 pm to 6 pm

Figure 4.4.2 (f) Opinion on the day lighting conditions in room 3 pm to 6 pm

Frequent activity in room				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Reading	15	48.4	48.4	48.4
Writing by hand	6	19.4	19.4	67.8
Working with laptop	3	9.7	9.7	77.5
Others	7	22.6	22.6	100
total	31	100	100	

Table 4.4.2 (g) Frequent activity in the room

Figure 4.4.2 (g) Frequent activity in the room

Frequently turn on the lamp (artificial lighting)				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Throughout the day	18	58.1	58.1	58.1
In the morning	4	12.9	12.9	71
In the evening	9	29	29	100
total	31	100	100	

Table 4.3.2 (i) use of the lamp (artificial lighting)

Fig 4.4.2 (i) use of the lamp (artificial lighting)

Frequent opening of the window during the day while studying				
	frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Yes	28	90.3	90.3	90.3
No	3	9.7	9.7	100
total	31	100	100	

Table 4.4.2 (j) Frequent opening of the window during the day while studying

Fig 4.4.2 (j) Frequent opening of the window during the day while studying

4.5 Lux Meter Data Sheet

4.5.1 IMO STATE UNIVERSITY GIRLS HOSTEL LUX METER READING

GROUND FLOOR

SIDE 1 IMSU GIRLS HOSTEL;						
TIME	8;00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
LUX						
Point 1	74.6	116.8	229.3	238.9	209.7	127.6
Point 2	69.2	115.8	284.1	279.9	289.2	242.6
Point 3	69.8	112.2	246.5	266.6	324.0	283.4
Point 4	51.7	99.4	118.0	159.5	183.5	158.6

Table 4.5.1(a) showing lux reading for Imo state university girls' hostel for the ground floor

FIRST FLOOR

SIDE 1 IMSU GIRLS HOSTEL;						
TIME	8;00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
LUX						
Point 1	74.6	110.6	234.4	239.5	213.4	131.5
Point 2	65.2	115.9	285.4	293.4	240.6	246.3
Point 3	67.6	114.5	237.9	269.3	323.9	290.7
Point 4	52.0	101.13	115.4	164.3	189.0	164.2

Table 4.5.1(b) showing lux reading for Imo state university girls' hostel for the first floor

SECOND FLOOR

SIDE 1 IMSU GIRLS HOSTEL;						
TIME	8;00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
LUX						
Point 1	67.3	122.2	220.4	232.4	271.1	166.6
Point 2	66.5	124.9	289.2	293.0	277.5	252.7
Point 3	63.6	100.9	216.7	287.2	410.7	283.6
Point 4	41.7	84.5	117.0	157.4	311.0	167.1

Table 4.5.1(c) showing lux reading for Imo state university girls' hostel for the second floor

Fig 4.5.1(a) showing the graph of lux reading of imsu girls hostel side 1

Figure 4.5.1(a) shows the graph on Lux reading at time intervals. Basically, the lux readings were taken by the researcher at every level, with each 4 points. The graph above only shows the average

of the reading. During the taking of the test the weather was sunny. The first reading was taken at 8.00 am and taken at an interval of every two hour until 6.00 pm. From the line graph above, the line of graph was increasing significantly across the time, and started to drop when the reading reaches 5.00 pm and went down at 6.00 pm. The ranges of lux reading were between 50 to 300 lx. According to Nigerian Standard (NS): 2017 “national building energy efficiency code” bedroom best illuminance is 100 (lx). However, bedroom in Hostels were not only use for sleeps and rest, it also works for reading and writing. There are no definite illuminance ranges for hostels categorized under Nigerian Standard (NS): 2017 “national building energy efficiency code”. Reading and writing” under Nigerian Standard are best at ranges of 200-400 (lx). In hostels, to sleep under illuminance that beyond 100 lux might be uncomfortable for students as it might increase temperature and glare, while doing reading or writing also might have the same comfortability issues.

GROUND FLOOR

SIDE 2 IMSU GIRLS HOSTEL;						
TIME	8;00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
LUX						
Point 1	110.3	163.1	523.6	746.2	1149.9	664.17
Point 2	91.3	115.8	262.3	348.0	385.8	217.2
Point 3	94.8	211.1	259.4	545.7	727.67	511.5
Point 4	94.0	133.4	321.3	436.2	482.3	445.2

Table 4.5.1(d)showing lux reading for Imo state university girls’ hostel for the ground floor

FIRST FLOOR

SIDE 2 IMSU GIRLS HOSTEL;						
TIME	8;00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
LUX						
Point 1	94.4	174.4	553.6	795.2	1111.5	695.3
Point 2	93.8	205.5	311.2	332.7	402.6	219.7
Point 3	97.4	215.9	217.6	543.6	729.8	542.4
Point 4	94.1	137.0	324.3	419.1	463.87	442.8

Table 4.5.1(d)showing lux reading for Imo state university girls’ hostel for the first floor

SECOND FLOOR

SIDE 2 IMSU GIRLS HOSTEL						
TIME	8:00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
LUX						
Point 1	104.13	173.8	541.3	728.7	1113.3	658.3
Point 2	94.9	203.9	262.6	332.3	408.67	221.03
Point 3	95.3	214.7	271.7	550.7	731.0	546.0
Point 4	94.1	131.2	324.4	422.4	480.3	428.0

Table 4.5.1(d) showing lux reading for Imo state university girls' hostel for the second floor

Fig 4.5.1(b) showing the graph of lux reading of imsu girls hostel side 2

Based on figure 4.5.1 (b), it shows line graph on side 2 of imsu girls' hostel. The “side 1” and “side 2” were indicated on the floor plan. On side 2 of imsu girls' hostel, this side facing the west where the sunset. The weather during the test were being taken is sunny. Based on the reading, the reading was quite higher than side 1. On every level, the line graph shows increasing line starts from 8.00 am to 4.00 pm and starts to drop after 4.00 pm. Most of the line has the highest peak reading at 4.00 pm. The decreased readings were drop very steep. The ranges of illuminance at side 2 of imsu girls' hostel are were between 98 - 700 (lx). It is obviously out of the recommended ranges of Nigerian standard.

4.5.2 MERIT HOSTEL LUX METER READING

GROUND FLOOR

SIDE 1 MERIT HOSTEL;						
TIME	8:00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
LUX						
Point 1	71.2	98.1	231.8	272.1	211.9	118.7
Point 2	65.7	92.6	243.3	269.2	173.8	107.6
Point 3	73.4	126.9	242.4	292.7	187.1	112.8
Point 4	50.4	90.9	183.8	194.1	124.4	110.0

Table 4.5.2(a) showing lux reading for merit hostel ground floor

FIRST FLOOR

SIDE 1 MERIT HOSTEL;						
TIME	8:00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
LUX						
Point 1	71.6	98.4	237.2	272.8	223.9	117.8
Point 2	64.3	92.1	245.9	271.6	177.5	109.7
Point 3	72.0	125.1	240.5	279.8	188.9	111.6
Point 4	51.5	91.5	184.1	193.8	121.8	108.6

Table 4.5.2(b) showing lux reading for merit hostel for the first floor

Fig 4.5.2 (a) showing the graph of lux reading of merit hostel side 1

Based on figure 4.5.2 (a), it shows lux reading of merit hostel side 1. This building has 2 levels. The weather during the test was sunny. The line graph shows the reading were increasing significantly started at 8.00 am reached its highest reading at 2 pm and slowly decrease after 4 pm and the reading were completely decrease steeply when reached 6 pm. The lowest reading taken were about 60 (lx). The ranges of reading taken on this case study were between 60 to 250 (lx). This ranges of reading do not intersect at any best recommended category under Nigerian standard

GROUND FLOOR

SIDE 2 MERIT HOSTEL;						
TIME	8:00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
LUX						
Point 1	65.7	121.0	213.7	319.4	262.0	119.6
Point 2	68.6	108.8	228.3	301.1	238.6	128.1
Point 3	71.5	118.0	222.0	274.2	218.8	129.0
Point 4	55.7	82.2	159.2	179.5	134.5	96.4

Table 4.5.2(c) showing lux reading for merit hostel side 2 ground floor

FIRST FLOOR

SIDE 2 MERIT HOSTEL;						
TIME	8:00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
LUX						
Point 1	76.3	121.2	215.8	341.4	296.2	141.1
Point 2	74.2	118.4	225.9	354.6	334.5	150.5
Point 3	56.1	120.7	204.2	341.8	256.6	138.2
Point 4	55.7	99.2	155.1	209.0	116.6	100.4

Table 4.5.2(d) showing lux reading for merit hostel side 2 for the first floor

Fig 4.5.2 (a) showing the graph of lux reading of merit hostel side 2

Figure 4.4.2 (b) shows side 2 of merit hostel, On each level, it can be seen that the reading reaches the highest at 2.00 pm. However, the illuminance still does not intersect at any of ranges of 300-400 (lx). The line graph shows the slowly increase reading started at 8.00 am and decrease slowly after 2.00pm. at level 1, the line graph shows that the reading at level 1 does not increase too much and its line graph almost like a linear line. The highest reading of illuminance recorded was only 290.3 (lx).

4.5.3 STEVE JAMES HOSTEL LUX METER READING

GROUND FLOOR

SIDE 1 STEVE JAMES;						
TIME	8:00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
LUX						
Point 1	73.3	164.7	330.4	381.7	290.0	141.8
Point 2	77.9	187.9	330.0	375.3	267.2	146.9
Point 3	64.2	116.8	267.2	199.1	115.6	92.6
Point 4	55.3	112.3	154.2	183.2	110.5	75.9

Table 4.5.3(a) showing lux reading for Steve James hostel ground floor

FIRST FLOOR

SIDE 1 STEVE JAMES;						
TIME	8:00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
LUX						
Point 1	73.6	164.4	331.8	392.0	328.2	140.9

Point 2	79.8	187.5	331.1	376.6	275.0	148.0
Point 3	65.9	143.6	269.6	200.7	116.9	90.1
Point 4	57.6	117.8	158.0	183.4	111.6	77.0

Table 4.5.3(b) showing lux reading for Steve James hostel for the first floor

SECOND FLOOR

SIDE 1 STEVE JAMES;						
TIME	8;00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
LUX						
Point 1	74.8	166.7	336.0	400.0	307.0	141.1
Point 2	80.6	187.7	333.3	385.8	284.5	152.7
Point 3	66.2	146.6	276.9	203.3	116.5	105.9
Point 4	58.4	120.4	161.5	184.1	114.0	94.7

Table 4.5.3(c) showing lux reading for Steve James hostel for the second floor

Fig 4.5.3 (a) showing the graph of lux reading of Steve James hostel side 1

Figure 4.4.3 (a) shows line graph of Steve James hostel 2 levels but start at level 2 . This zone faces the sunrise. However, sunlight from sunrise is not very bright compared to sunlight during sunset. The duration of sunrise also usually does not take too much time. This is the reason why the reading at the morning does not appear high. The highest reading taken was 270.9 (lx). The increasing of the line graph was dramatically slowly. The same goes to its decreasing reading.

GROUND FLOOR

SIDE 2 STEVE JAMES HOSTEL						
TIME LUX	8;00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
Point 1	32.9	60.3	77.6	49.6	20.6	8.8
Point 2	28.2	61.7	102.1	49.6	22.9	9.0
Point 3	20.3	25.6	58.3	46.2	23.4	8
Point 4	18.9	24.2	57.2	35.2	20.4	7.4

Table 4.5.3(c) showing lux reading for merit hostel side 2 ground floor

FIRST FLOOR

SIDE 2 STEVE JAMES HOSTEL						
TIME LUX	8;00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
Point 1	33.6	60.6	77.3	50.8	21.9	8.9
Point 2	729.0	62.0	103.3	50.2	23.8	9.4
Point 3	21.3	28.9	59.6	47.3	24.5	8.4
Point 4	19.0	26.7	62.0	35.5	21.1	7.4

Table 4.5.3(d) showing lux reading for merit hostel side 2 for the first floor

SECOND FLOOR

SIDE 2 STEVE JAMES;						
TIME LUX	8;00 am	10:00 am	12:00 pm	2:00 pm	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
Point 1	34.4	61.4	79.2	52.2	22.9	8.9
Point 2	29.8	63.2	107.3	51.7	25.4	9.2
Point 3	22.9	30.0	61.3	48.4	24.6	7.9
Point 4	20.3	27.4	61.1	36.4	22.1	8.5

Table 4.5.3(e) showing lux reading for merit hostel side 2 for the second floor

Fig 4.5.3 (b) showing the graph of lux reading of Steve James hostel side 2

Line graph as in figure 4.4.3 (b) is completely different than other line graphs. This graph shows a very steep increase and reaches its peak at 12.00 pm. After 12 pm, the line graph appears to suddenly decrease. The weather that day was sunny. According to Nigerian standards, the ranges on the reading were only suitable for sleep and rest. These dark circumstances can lead the hostel occupant to turn on the lamp throughout the day. The highest reading taken was 72.98 (lx).

CHAPTER 5; SUMMARY, RECOMMENDATIONS, AND CONCLUSION

5.1 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Some of the results of the interviews are outlined and discussed. On the activity the students most frequently carry out in the hostels, fifteen (46%) out of the 86 respondents chose reading and writing by hand, while 8 students chose working with the computer. Furthermore, 56 out of the 86-respondent said that they studied more in their rooms. Knowledge about the use of lighting (natural or artificial) in the hostels revealed that 75% of the respondents made use of artificial lighting throughout the day. This is understandable since the measured illuminances were really low. The Illuminance levels of 400 to 500 lux are recommended for desktop activities (reading and writing). The health complaints (headache, eyestrain and itching, etc.) by 30% of the respondents could also be linked to the low illuminance levels within the spaces. Students who frequently remain and learn in their rooms during power outages could be the ones with more complaints.

5.2 CONCLUSION FROM THE FINDINGS

Questions regarding user behavior (the operation of windows to bring in natural light) resulted in over 80% of the students saying that they were able to operate the windows and use the shades (curtains) to improve upon their visual comfort. Rooms that are oriented towards the east and west could be observed to have the curtains in place to block direct and reflected solar radiation. This practice however, has the consequence that occupants then resort to the use of artificial lighting which could have energy penalties. The impact of switching on the light ‘all the time’ was mostly felt by students who had to bear the cost of their consumed electricity.

5.3 IMPLICATION OF FINDINGS

Based on researcher’s observation and questionnaires that was being distributed to students, the design features and problems that influence the lighting in hostels were identified. They are;

- The orientation of some of the building does not faces the direct sunlight which causes the sunlight does not intersect at any recommended ranges of illuminance based on Nigerian Standards.
- Some building causes glare at peak hour, and some receives just right and some very low illuminance.
- Students also suffered from certain health constraints and most of it was eyestrain.

- A nature obstacle such as surrounding buildings placed too close to the hostel influences the diffusion of natural lighting into the window.

5.4 SUGGESTION FOR FURTHER STUDIES

The study had the objective of evaluating light in students' hostels. This was because of the often-poor designs that are created for students to use as hostels, without considering the use of sustainable design principles and occupants' comfort. Through questions and empirical measurements, data was accrued which indicated poor illuminance levels in the spaces of the hostels and health complaints by the building occupants.

5.5 RECOMMENDATION AND SUMMARY

To alleviate the deteriorating effect of bad lighting conditions in the hostels (future buildings), the following should be considered:

- The education of students and landlords (hostel owners) about the positive effects and benefits of natural lighting;
- The rolling-up of window curtains especially in the afternoons as an effective means to allow light to penetrate into a space should be enhanced. Students should be taught to understand that it is of more importance to allow natural light into a space than to decorate the room with curtains;
- Natural lighting should be made the prior means of lighting hostels in the day by institutionalizing strict policies which oblige designers of hostels to adhere to the use of recommendations for sizing windows, the use of materials with high reflectance values and the use of sustainable design principles.
- These measures when applied could help improve upon the comfort of students, their well-being and help reduce energy consumption of buildings in Owerri. Future hostel buildings could also benefit from the application of the recommended measures.

Reference

1. Agency, i. E. (2001). Application guide for daylight responsive lighting .
2. Branch, o. S. (2008). Lighting assessment at the workplace. Hongkong: labor department.
3. Choi, j. H., Beltran, l. O., & Kim, h. S. (2012). Impacts of indoor daylight environments on patient average length of stay (ALOS) in healthcare facility. *Building and environment* , 50, 65-7.
4. Dr peter, l. (2012). A skylight can admit more than three times as much light as a vertical window of the same size. 127-129.
5. Federal ministry of power, w. A. (2017). Building energy efficiency guideline for Nigeria. Abuja: federal ministry of power, works and housing (housing) Shehu yar'adua way, .
6. Ferna, e. (2012). Computers and graphics inverse lighting design for interior buildings integrating natural and artificial sources. *Computer and graphics*, 36,1096-1108.
7. Hk., g. B. (2007). Daylight utilization. Retrieved from <http://gbtech.emsd.gov.hk/english/minimize/daylight.html>
8. Inc., o. B. (1997). "see better, feel better, look better.". California: Ott bio light systems, Inc. .
9. Kay, b. (2009, 12 23). Natural lighting needs intelligence and control. Retrieved from <https://www.buildings.com/article-details/articleid/9253/title/natural-lighting-needs-intelligence-and-control.aspx>
10. Koranteng, c., & Simons, b. (2012). An evaluation of natural lighting levels in students' hostels in a suburb of Kumasi, Ghana. 548-554.
11. Li, d., Cheung, h., Cheung, k., & lam, n. (2010). Determination of vertical daylight illuminance under non-overcast sky conditions. *Building and environment*, 498-508.
12. Loe, d. (1999). Lighting design for school. https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/276707/building_bulletin_90_lighting_design_for_schools.pdf , pp. 1-86. Retrieved from https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/276707/building_bulletin_90_lighting_design_for_schools.pdf
13. Nnadozie, c. F., Njoku, d. I., Onu, u. L., & Anyanwu, o. M. (2017). Indoor air quality levels of some criteria pollutants in university hostel in Nigeria. *International journal for scientific research and development*, 681-685.
14. Phillips, d. (2004). Daylighting; natural light in architecture. Massachusetts: architectural press Burlington.

15. Ramirez, e., Casares, f. J., Ramirez-faz, j., & Lopez-Luque, r. (2013). Development of a suitable synthetic projection to simultaneously study solar exposure and natural lighting in building windows. *Energy and buildings*, 65,391-397.
16. Salata, f., Vollaro, a. D., & Ferraro, a. (2014). An economic perspective on the reliability of lighting systems in building with highly efficient energy . A case studies *Energy conversion and management*, 84, 623-632.
17. Yeh, s. C. (2014). A natural lighting system using a prismatic daylight collector. *Lighting research and technology*, 502-512.